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Editor's note

In this second issue of the Critical Point newsletter from MeCCS, we address the issue of natural resources from different perspectives. We live on a vast planet that we have forgotten that it also has limits. This illusion of infinity brings us closer to the inflexion points or tipping points that once exceeded, leading a system to practically irreversible changes, from which we can hardly go back. Knowledge of these critical points is very valuable for the design and implementation of sustainable trajectories. We believe that being aware of the limits, connectivity and complexity of our environment can help us build more critical and informed thinking for better decision-making at all scales.

In this issue, you will find two informative articles about resources, their relationship with CO₂ capture and storage systems, as well as the social and environmental impacts that are related to resources. We've also put together a couple of infographics that will give you more food for thought on these topics in the *Yes, yes, it is* section. In the *CO₂NVERSING* section, we present to you the interview with MSc Rodrigo García Herrera from the National Laboratory of Sustainability Sciences of the UNAM Institute of Ecology with whom we spoke about another way of conceiving resources, their use and management. In our final section, *Take Away*, we leave you a list of materials, books, documentaries and conferences that we recommend to expand your knowledge on these topics. We hope you enjoy this edition and, if you wish, contact us to share your comments and topics of interest.

Rivers, water and something else

By Alejandra De León Ibarra

When we take an element of nature to put it to use, and generate some benefit or profit, at that moment, we turn it into a resource. As we know, the different elements of nature –biotic or abiotic–, are distributed in a heterogeneous way on our planet. Therefore, access to them can be simpler or more complicated depending on their location, quantity, timing and type of technology available for their extraction and exploitation.

Throughout the history of humanity, the exploitation of natural resources has been increasing due to the pressure generated by the increase of population in ecosystems, which is associated with excessive demand for goods and services. We have reached a critical point where the quantity and quality of resources have decreased considerably, making their finitude and vulnerability evident. An example of this is that, nowadays, the soils are too polluted to generate good quality food and that the amount of freshwater is insufficient, even to cover some basic needs in certain regions.

Perhaps it is worth remembering that resources are more than just a currency or objects to gain some benefit. Rivers, for example, are one of the main sources of freshwater that runs through the earth's surface and that, throughout history, have borne great anthropogenic pressure due to the need for human access to this resource. Water has allowed us to produce food, as well as to meet cleaning and consumption needs. In addition, it provides sites for recreation and has a spiritual meaning in many cultures.

It is enough to take a look at history and “river” civilizations – Mesopotamia, Egypt and China – to understand the importance of the relationship between water and humanity. Beyond its usefulness, the human being has found fascination with water (and its properties such as color, shape, strength, and fluidity) and therefore we find all kinds of metaphors and symbolism in art and religion. Perhaps one of the most beautiful examples in America is the Amazon River: about 7 million square kilometers connect eight South American countries and is home to a great diversity and native peoples that have coexisted in harmony with the river for centuries.

In arid or semi-arid ecosystems there are perennial rivers that carry water throughout the year and there are also rivers that do not carry water during the dry season, which are known as intermittent rivers. These intermittent rivers can store a certain volume of water during the rest of the year, or they help keep groundwater very close to the surface. Thus, the living beings of the ecosystem have access to water resources at a time that is critical for their survival. In the case of Mexico, we have 569,000 kilometers of rivers, of which 149,300 are of intermittent currents and 420,500 correspond to perennial currents.

Our planet is undergoing a rapid process of change that can transform the way things work. In 2006, Dr. Andrea Bolongaro (3) argued that with climate change and lack of rain, a large percentage of perennial rivers could become intermittent. So we ask ourselves, what is the ecological importance of rivers for ecosystems and society?

Rivers play a key role in maintaining other natural resources such as soil, air, flora and fauna. That is why we can call them riparian corridors since particular vegetation and conditions are associated with them. These corridors are essential for a large number of physical, abiotic and biotic processes (1) that contribute to the rest of the ecosystems of which they are part. Vegetation in these zones is influenced by the characteristics of surface water flows, such as seasonality, magnitude, frequency and duration of certain events, as well as by groundwater flows, spring discharges (2) and processes related to hyporheic zones where surface water and groundwater mix. Other factors that have an effect on the riparian zones are the geomorphology of the land, types of soil, geological structures, and extension of the flood zones, among others. As you will see, it is not just a stream of water that follows the "easiest" path, but a whole set of interrelated elements.

Vegetation of riparian corridors is usually more diverse and abundant than that of the rest of the ecosystem in which they are immersed, especially in semi-arid ecosystems where vegetation on the banks of rivers obtains more water during the year. This has the consequence that the trees and shrubs that are located in these areas are larger and leafier. In the dry season, these corridors become a refuge for animals and are suitable sites for the reproduction, rearing and protection of microorganisms, insects, fish, amphibians, birds and land mammals.

Oh! Apparently, human beings are not the only ones who seek to take advantage of the opportunity to prosper on the banks of a river, but we are also on the list of vulnerable species in the face of the consequences of poor management of the resource or the effects of the environment on it.

In addition to all of the above, another important contribution to riparian corridors has to do with the physicochemical processes that allow the capture and storage of carbon dioxide (CO₂). You may be wondering how. Atmospheric CO₂ is captured by vegetation, through photosynthesis, and stored in the soil as organic matter thanks to microorganisms that generate organic carbon. Part of this carbon is used in various biological processes in the soil and a percentage returns to the atmosphere as CO₂. Rivers also contribute through the process of weathering, through which water alters the chemical composition of rocks and can also carry carbon molecules and other elements in solution from one place to another.

The wonder of resources is that, although we don't always realize it, they offer a wide range of goods and services, not only to humans but to other beings within ecosystems. Whether it is a resource that flows (such as water) or one that is stored (such as minerals and hydrocarbons), there are connections between systems to which they belong and whose operation is essential to know and understand in order to properly manage them. Just as thousands of species have learned to coexist under the dynamics of riparian corridors, so we must learn to live on a planet where resources are finite, intermittent and on which we all depend.

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WAR CONFLICTS, THE CARBON FOOTPRINT AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH RESOURCES

By **Carolina Contreras González**

Every day we hear words that reflect the reality of the times in which we live: wars, crises, inequality, poverty. Given the crudeness of these terms, we seek compensation when we speak of sustainability, resilience, peace, prosperity and equality, but these words are less frequent than the former; they are less real. We find ourselves in a contest to see who has more and then we think that the problem is solved by sharing a little of what we have (although not much) with others, without thinking about the limits of what we have.

And here we are, century after century, repeating the same dynamic since we learned to accumulate and possess, with the idea that this would ensure us food and a way to survive. We create mechanisms to defend what is ours. We have spent about 10,000 years devising more sophisticated ways to generate more, consume more... and have advantages over others. We stop needing to start ambitioning. We design social structures to differentiate and organize ourselves, but also to divide and exclude us. Also, in this social framework, we create things and situations that leave nothing and no one out.

Regarding these forms of inclusion, war is also inclusive. Yes! It harms everything in its path: people, their activities, their interests, and also the environment. It is a genocide and a massacre of the ecosphere. Although its origin is diffuse in the sociopolitical and economic contexts, it is an act of massive indiscriminate aggression against others, of the other. Nothing is gained and, on the contrary, there is an enormous deterioration of the social fabric and of the ecosystems. It is not surprising that most wars are associated with the underlying power of expansionism simply to possess that which we do not have, but that we "need".

Now, if we talk about pollution, the situation is slightly different. Like war conflicts, the original problem is related to human activities or is, rather, one of its many consequences: some of them are daily, and apparently, less offensive. Daily activities that seem not to affect anyone can be harmful when, for example, it is necessary to use a means of transport (internal combustion or even electric). Although it seems like a harmless act toward others, one would have to ask what is the impact on the environment. Isn't Mother Earth someone?

On average, moving from one place to another in a private vehicle (cars, motorcycles or taxis) makes us responsible for 21% of global CO₂ emissions. And what about other even less common activities, such as launching rockets that, although they do not affect the lives of others, do compromise environmental health. In fact, there are no more than 100 launches of these artifacts per year with a footprint of 300 tons of CO₂ for each one, but they are added to the list of pernicious acts towards Gaia. There are plenty of examples of human activities to make it clear that they are the main cause of pollution and environmental deterioration. The carbon footprint generated from them has a significant effect on the environment.

Back to the point and to distribute responsibilities, it is no coincidence that the five countries that emit the most CO₂ into the atmosphere (China, the United States, India, Russia and Japan) are the most powerful in military matters. And if we look at the past, of the almost five years that the First World War lasted (1914-1918) and among the 30 countries that participated, the Triple Entente (Russia, the United Kingdom and France) released approximately 4.14 billion tons of CO₂, almost the same amount of emissions added up that were emitted by Russia, Japan and all the countries of the African continent in one year. In World War II (1939-1945), the countries that led the conflict between the Allies (Great Britain, the Soviet Union and the United States) and the Axis (Berlin-Rome-Tokyo) released 24.75 billion tons of CO₂, which is equivalent to two-thirds of the total global carbon released in 2020.

After World War II, science and technology developed significantly, which brought with it the development and manufacture of highly hydrocarbon-dependent weapons. This fact facilitated and increased its consumption, and with it, the contribution of large amounts of CO₂ to the atmosphere. In this way, other problems were triggered to ensure access to hydrocarbons with a strong impact, especially in the Middle East, but which has not left out other regions in Africa, Latin America or Asia. Other subsequent conflicts put the countries that participated in the Vietnam War (the United States, Russia and China) at the top with a total of 4.58 billion tons of CO₂ in the year alone, marking the beginning of sustained climate change in the world of the twentieth century.

Currently, we can measure the carbon footprint of each war or social conflict to try to measure its impact on the planet. However, this measure is insufficient to quantify the degradation and damage caused by humanity. Throughout history, we have several examples of how the search for resources motivated us to create technology, and innovations, support science and go beyond our own limits in order to reach the desired treasure. In order to gain an advantage, oceans have been crossed by ships to claim territories that were already inhabited, or expeditions have been organized to explore from the great mountains to the seabed to collect information. Wars and conquests have devastated people, culture, knowledge, the earth and everything that inhabits it.

Nowadays, the conflict between Russia and Ukraine is a reminder of the fights that are sought to give meaning or justification. And yet, every such decision is a stab at Mother Earth. Natural gas is the fuel with the least environmental impact because its emissions are between 40 and 50% lower than those of coal. For this reason, the closure of one of the Russian gas pipelines changes the dynamics of fuel supply to Europe, and the scarcity of this resource is leading the countries that depend on it to reconsider the consumption of other fuels that generate enormous amounts of CO₂: coal, oil and its derivatives (8.4 million tons of carbon dioxide per year).

Outside of being a solution, it makes the problem bigger. Although there are technologies such as CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) that would make energy and industrial processes somewhat "cleaner" despite the use of fossil fuels, the setback regarding the decarbonization commitments of the economies could lead us to a point of no return. Now we can see that it is not only about depleting, polluting or degrading resources such as water, minerals, hydrocarbons, forests or culture but that we are also running down our carbon budget. All our activities deplete that other virtually invisible resource a little more.

Wars, conflicts, and strife are planned misdeeds that, no matter what the cause, seem intended to trample on human and environmental rights. And so I return to the question that Slavoj Žižek poses in his essay; *Are we at war? Do we have an enemy?*: "Terrorism is the common denominator of all social ills. How then are we supposed to escape from this situation?" The political and economic interests in the proclamation of maintaining the world order under the scathing justification and the duty of "keeping the peace", as well as combating disturbances that alter the security of nations, have left millions dead and the annihilation of biodiversity. . Who do we have as an enemy and how many solutions are we capable of proposing to escape from the situation in which we ourselves have gotten ourselves? What is the footprint we are leaving and what new metrics will we invent to dismiss it?

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CONVERSANDO

CONVERSING

How and in what are we spending what's left on?

An interview with **Rodrigo García Herrera**

By **Paola Massyel García Meneses**

The resources that this planet has are finite. The form of consumption of the human being is perceived as insatiable. This pattern has accelerated the use of fossil fuels, minerals, metals and biomass and it has been calculated that these rates will continue to increase in the coming decades. It is projected that by 2050 we will use around 140 million tons each year from the last three groups mentioned above. The Administrator of the United Nations Development Program and president of the Sustainable Development Group, Achim Steiner comments that "People believe that environmental damage is the price that must be paid for the economic development of goods. However, we cannot and it is not necessary to continue acting as if this dilemma is inevitable". This association is very important because the population uses and inhabits this planet and the effects of this mismanagement of resources are turning towards an increase in direct harmful impacts on human populations and all their other inhabitants.

Pandemics, the effects of climate change (hurricanes, heat waves, frosts, floods, droughts), loss of biodiversity and desertification are examples of phenomena and processes that we face as humanity, all of them directly linked to the misuse of resources. This makes us think and ask ourselves if there are other lifestyles and options that can be empathic with the environment. Where should we be investing finite resources, such as fossil fuels, to seek more sustainable lifestyles?

We talked about this topic with the MSc Rodrigo García Herrera. Rodrigo is mainly interested in agent-based modeling, platform economies, self-organization, self-management, and free software. He believes that sociocultural transformation towards sustainable development paths can be helped by the careful design of online platforms. Rodrigo is a skilled software developer with experience in both industry and academia and believes that some of the problems we are facing today can be better framed and solved through bottom-up systems engineering. bottom-up).

National Laboratory of Sustainability Sciences, Institute of Ecology of UNAM.

P- What approaches could serve for better use and management of planetary resources?

R- By "better use" I mean a way to achieve a smooth transition to a lifestyle that we've already promised anyway. Whether it's because fossil fuels run out or the planet overheats: sooner or later **we will have to live differently**. We don't know yet how that lifestyle will be like, but we do know that it will be frugal compared to how we live now: no sports cars, no transatlantic travel.

The life that awaits us in many ways resembles the life that our ancestors had. It has always been normal to move little, to be thrifty. What is abnormal is the 150th anniversary of the oil era! Although relatively short, in 150 years a lot of inertia accumulated. For example, some production systems, from which our food comes, yield one calorie in the form of food for every seven that are used in hydrocarbon derivatives. The end of the oil age could lead to terrible conflicts.

I think we have to do everything we can to smooth out the changes that are inevitable. I like how they say it in Totnes **"transition is another way of saying revolution but without the connotation of a million dead"**.

P- How do we make those transitions, how do we smooth them out?

R- We face problems with different levels, and therefore it is appropriate to speak of transitions, in the plural. I can think of a way to encourage some transitions that go through computing and informatics because they are topics that interest me. But it is important to clarify that these are not universal recipes to heal our ills. They are nothing more than an approach to an important aspect of the crisis we face: **organization**. Because, although the civilizing crisis manifests itself in the environment, it is not an environmental problem, it is a problem of organizing life in the Common Home. And it seems to me that the Internet is something new under the sun, in the sense of “there is nothing new under the sun.” The premise is that **among many we achieve more**, but coordination of human beings has an energetic cost.

The Great Corporation or the State are organizational systems that, due to their size and income, can afford such coordination. And out of malice or clumsiness, they have historically done it to the great detriment of all (and the great benefit of the elites). That is why states are capable of mobilizing armies of hundreds of thousands of people. That is why big corporations can destroy entire ecosystems. However, the internet and contemporary computing allow us to balance the distribution of power. They allow us to smooth out organizational costs and join us where we were previously atomized. Use our strength in numbers: **we are many, they are few**.

Consider the example of Amazon, an organization that has produced the biggest mega-billionaire of our time. Their superpower is the computer platform with which they essentially solve logistics problems linked to distribution. Owners of their platform, it is natural that they develop it to embody their value system which, as far as we can see, are not very virtuous and subordinate to the maximum value of increasing profit margin. Well, there is nothing to prevent us from developing our own platform, embodying our own value system. It's perfectly legal and we can make it a good deal.

By the way, I think it is important to make it a good business because it is easier to convince someone to earn more or spend less than it is to convince someone to demonstrate in the streets or talk to their legislator. As Lawrence Lessig wrote: code is law. Software, the algorithm that so many fear and regret, rules our public life. So, **let's take control** of that software, let's make it our own, let's develop and use our own software.

P- What values should our software incorporate?

R- I think of those that Fritjof Capra contrasts with the idea of outdated values. Instead of competition, cooperation; instead of expansion, conservation; instead of exploitation, nutrition. Or perhaps those of ParEcon¹: equity, solidarity, diversity, self-management, efficiency and sustainability. Perhaps we would write software to articulate the institutions that Michael Albert proposes such as participatory planning, consumption councils, balanced work systems and the others that are suggested for a post-capitalist life.

P- Will it be possible to develop platforms to smooth the costs of horizontal, cellular, self-managed organization?

R- There are computer problems around La Buena Vida, there are possible apps that help to work with hands and the brain, and also with the company of neighbors and friends, in meaningful and satisfying tasks. I think we would do well to use the solar energy stored in hydrocarbons to develop those platforms, to create those organizations.

¹**ParEcon** (*Participatory economics*) or participatory economy is a proposed economic system that uses participatory decision-making as an economic mechanism in a given society. It arises from the work of the political theorist Michael Albert, and the radical economist Robin Hahnel, between the 80's and 90's. This is a liberal alternative proposal to today's capitalist market economies, to centrally planned socialism.

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

In this issue, we present some critical data to reflect on the role of resources in the environment and society. Then you will find an infographic about the classification, organization and management of natural resources complemented by a series of sentences that will allow you to continue reflecting on the interactions and relationships in our environment, those that we see and those that we do not see as well.

Key Facts to understand connectivity and indivisibility of the resources

The management, use and exploitation of resources have direct and indirect effects on environmental, sociopolitical, technological and economic systems; that is, all the contexts we depend on and are part of.

DID YOU KNOW THAT...

<p>Currently, 70% more natural resources are extracted than 20 years ago.</p> <p>(1)</p>		<p>90% of biodiversity loss and water stress are a consequence of resource extraction and processing.</p> <p>(2)</p>	<p>In the last 60 years, at least 40% of all international conflicts have been linked to the use of natural resources.</p> <p>(3)</p>
<p>Humanity is depleting ecosystems at a rate roughly 1.7 times higher than the regeneration capacity of the planet.</p> <p>(6)</p>	<p>pollution of land, air and water from unsustainable consumption and production cause major health problems, especially in poor countries.</p> <p>(7)</p>		<p>In 2016, environmental degradation in Mexico was 6 times greater than the actions aimed at protecting it.</p> <p>(8)</p>

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What we see and what we don't see

Let's talk about resources...

Resources are elements of nature that allow generating benefits or profits when used and that help improve people's quality of life.

Features

Utility: they are used to satisfy a need of those who consume it.

Limited availability: depend on the existence, accessibility and demand.

Depletion potential: Gradually depleted as they are used.

Classification

- Biotic and abiotic.
- Flow and stock.
- Probable, proven, possible and current

Biomass

Coal and minerals

Oil

Natural gas

Natural Resources

Geotherma

Solar radiation

Water

Air/wind

Soils

Technology and innovation can help us transform nature into a resource

Resources are not Distributed equally

How are resources organized and managed?

Access to resources, their management, their distribution and the costs associated with these activities can be sources of social conflict and cause damage to ecosystems.

The excludability of the resources refers to how easy or difficult it is to access them, while the subtractability concerns their level of extraction or exploitation.

In order not to exceed a temperature increase of 2°C, it is necessary to REDUCE carbon intensity by 6.5% each year from 2016 to 2100.

		Subtractability	
		High	Low
Excludability	Easy	Private goods	Recursos de peaje
	Difficult	Common-pool resources	Public goods

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And where is the CO₂?

Until now, CO₂ is considered a greenhouse gas whose high concentrations in the atmosphere have strong impacts on the planet's climate dynamics.

Although we do not see it, CO₂ is distributed through various subsystems such as the biosphere, hydrosphere, lithosphere, and atmosphere.

Today, the needs related to its management and use could change the way we think about it.

Is CO₂ an invisible resource?

We invite you to reflect on the following ideas while you find the words that complement them in the alphabet soup:

- 1- CO₂ is an element that is found _____ in the various planetary subsystems (biosphere, atmosphere, lithosphere, hydrosphere).
- 2 - A mature _____ has the capacity to absorb 21 kg of CO₂ per year.
- 3 - Natural and anthropological processes can cause the _____ of soils, affecting their ability to absorb CO₂.
- 4 - 300 million years ago, in the _____, the great deposits of coal that we exploit today were formed.
- 5 - Before plants conquered the mainland, more than 450 million years ago, the concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere was 8 times _____ what it is today.
- 6 - The pollution of the seas and bodies of water reduces their capacity of _____ of CO₂.
- 7 - _____ generation associated with fossil fuels is responsible for more than 70% of CO₂ emissions.
- 8 - Among the natural alternatives to control emissions are reforestation and the enrichment of _____.
- 9 - The capture and storage of CO₂ is a _____ alternative for the control of emissions of anthropogenic origin or direct capture from the air.
- 10 - According to the IPCC, the emissions we have left in the _____ of carbon to limit the increase in temperature to 1.5° C are 420 gigatons.

e t e g d u b z e l w q a
 t n q g t e n g r a u z b
 c a r b o n i f e r o u s
 o t p o w e r v e g c x o
 a u w z b r n m r e l p r
 l r a v z g t s t r o o p
 j a j i x y l f y u t i t
 k l e s d i r c g h e k i
 p l q x o a w i n d w j o
 n y m s u n u y m t x b n
 l a c i g o l o n h c e t

Answers: 1. naturally, 2. tree, 3. degradation, 4. Carboniferous, 5. larger, 6. absorption, 7. Power, 8. soils, 9. technological, 10. budget.

References:

- <https://airelibre.cl/cuanto-carbono-absorbe-arbol/>
- <http://www.fao.org/soils-portal/soil-degradation-restoration/en/>
- <https://www.pnas.org/content/99/7/4167>
- <https://skepticalscience.com/CO2-levels-during-the-late-Ordovician.html>
- <https://www.mcc-berlin.net/en/research/co2-budget.html>

PARA LLEVAR TAKE-AWAY

In our list of recommendations for this two-month period, we include information about conferences, reference sites (atlases and maps), documentaries and films, as well as books that address the subject of natural resources from different perspectives.

Annual Conference: Scottish CCS / Net-zero boundaries and borders: where do we draw the line?

On Tuesday, June 21, 2022, the annual conference of the Scottish CCS will be held in which, over 5 sessions, carbon across borders, low-carbon hydrogen and CCS, negative emissions and CO2 removal will be discussed, CCS in Scotland and carbon offset markets. The event will be in hybrid mode and is completely free. If you want to know more about the agenda, speakers and registration form, check the following link:

<https://scs.org.uk/news-events/events/148-sccs-annual-conference-2022-netzero-boundaries-and-borders-where-do-we-draw-the-line>

The carbon map

This website displays an animated, distorted, colored interactive map to convey the role of different countries in climate change. The data comes from public databases of governments, industries and international organizations

<https://www.carbonmap.org/?lang=es>

Environmental Justice Atlas

Georeferenced database that integrates information about social conflicts related to the industry and extraction of natural resources around the world. The project has the participation of international experts from 23 universities and environmental justice organizations from 18 countries. It is coordinated by the Autonomous University of Barcelona.

<https://ejatlas.org/>

Short Documentaries: *The Topic* / *The Gulf Stream*

Six short documentaries about the climate crisis in Mexico related to water, air, oceans, energy, coal and food. A documentary miniseries under the direction and production of Gael García Bernal and the writer and linguist Yásnaya Aguilar that presents different stories and perspectives of these problems.

<https://lacorrientedelgolfo.net/proyecto/el-tema/>

Documentary: *The Curse of Abundance*

This documentary addresses what has happened when money and morals collide to influence decision-making in the Yasuní Park in the Ecuadorian Amazon, a biodiversity paradise where several indigenous communities live and which is a space where some of the largest oil reserves in that country.

<https://www.primevideo.com/detail/La-maldici%C3%B3n-de-la-abundancia/0GI0KBK6CNUT2AU56ZJPOVQUA8>

Series: *Explained - The End of Oil*

This chapter of the series "In a nutshell" shows how the discovery and use of oil allowed great advances, but it has also been the cause of great inequalities. An explanation is also given here as to why, despite the negative impacts of this resource, we continue to use it.

<https://www.netflix.com/search?q=explained&jbv=80216752>

Series: *Story / Level 1 - The Middle East Oil*

This chapter in the series "History: Level 1" includes facts about oil in the Middle East and invites us to ask ourselves if this resource is a blessing or a curse. Although the subject is focused on the analysis of social and environmental impacts related to the discovery of oil fields, it is also applicable to any other natural resource.

<https://www.netflix.com/search?q=explained&jbv=80216752>

Book: *Small is Beautiful, a study of economics as if people mattered*

Published in 1973 by the economist E.F.Schumacher, this book presents a different way of approaching the objectives of the economy and proposes an alternative vision for the proper use of human and natural resources, development and forms of organization, inspired by various sources of information, philosophies and experiences.

Book: *The limits to growth, the 30-year update*

In this update, 30 years after the first publication of the book *The Limits to Growth* (1972), Donella Meadows, Dennis Meadows and Jorgen Randers reaffirm their thesis about the importance of proposing political, social and economic solutions based on the limits to growth of our societies in a world of finite resources.

Mexico City, Mexico, 2022